

ePIC Simulation Data Retention Policy - Draft

Starting in June 2025, simulation productions older than six months will be archived to tape storage unless they are integral to a project deliverable, such as the Technical Design Report, or to a publication where results need to be reproduced.

Simulation productions for project deliverables and publications will remain readily accessible to the collaboration for the lifetime of the ePIC project, while other productions will be archived but still retained. The leadership team, along with the Publication Committee and the Conference and Talks Committee, will identify which simulation productions need to remain always accessible.

The six-month period ensures that the active set of simulation data is recent enough to incorporate important updates without disrupting ongoing detector and physics studies.

Six months was chosen as an appropriate data lifetime under current conditions, with a rapidly evolving software base that quickly renders older data obsolete and limited storage resources. This retention period may be extended in the future as the software stabilizes and additional storage becomes available.